

Simulation tutorial

Here we describe the code for applying the simulation methods to estimating the optimal search time following “A framework for modeling the impacts of searcher behavior on the efficiency of abundance surveys”. Here we briefly describe examples from using the `mrds` package (distance sampling) and the `unmarked` package (occupancy analysis and N-mixture models).

The basic idea of this approach is to simulate a bunch of datasets from the selected design with known time budget parameters (to determine how many sites are completed and the detection probability) and density (or probability of occurrence). We then used the simulations to get the density estimates range of potential search times and get the average CV or standard error for each search time. We caution that simulation can be slow.

Distance sampling with MRDS

Our first example using the `mrds` package will explore distance sampling using the halfnormal detection function, though this can be changed to the exponential or hazard functions. The full code is given in `MRDS_halfnorm_example.R`. Here we walk through the code, first we need to define the necessary simulation parameters below.

```
##Simulate new dataset
library(mrds) #load the mrds library
source("Sim_funcs.R") #load functions needed for simulating distance data.

B <- 1e3 #reps for standard error estimates

ts.vec <- 10^seq(-5, -1, length.out=20) #search times to explore

#specificity time budget
t0 <- 0.1 #transect setup time
th <- 0.01 #handling time of a detection
tt <- 10 #total search time

#specify density and overdispersion
dens <- 10 #true target density
alpha <- 1 #degree of overdispersion in targets

#probability of detection
beta <- 0.01 #searcher inefficiency

#transect info
length <- 10 #length of transect
trans.hwidth <- 1 #half-width of transect
A <- length*2*trans.hwidth #area of a transect

#model info
model <- "halfnorm"
```

Once these terms have been defined we can iterate through all the potential search times and calculate the

```

se.vec <- cv.vec <- numeric(length(ts.vec))

for(j in 1:length(ts.vec)) {
  ts <- ts.vec[j]
  #get the probability of detection for this ts
  p <- p.detect(ts=ts, beta=beta)

  #find half.width for halfnormal that gives the correct p for this search time.
  sig <- exp(optimize(f=mrds_objective_fun, interval=c(-10, 10), p=p, w=trans.hwidth,
                    case="halfnorm")$minimum)

  #go run a bunch of simulations to get values for se(nhat)
  nhat.vec <- numeric(B)
  for(i in 1:B) {
    #The sim.distance function smulates transects until total time reaches tt.
    #Returns the estimated density
    Dhat.vec[i] <- sim.distance(t0, ts, th, tt, dens, alpha, beta, sig, trans.hwidth, A)
  }

  se.vec[j] <- sd(Dhat.vec, na.rm=TRUE)
  cv.vec[j] <- sd(Dhat.vec, na.rm=TRUE)/mean(Dhat.vec, na.rm=TRUE)
}

```

Below we plot the results from this simulation. The optimal search time here is $\tau_S^* = 0.0008$.

Figure 1: Relative uncertainty in occupancy survey for different search times in an distance survey. Minimum of the curve corresponds to the optimal search time.

Occupancy survey with unmarked

Now we walk through another example using an occupancy survey. In this case we will use the `unmarked` package for estimation.

```

library(unmarked)
source("Sim_funcs.R")

```

```

method    <- "occu" #type of survey design
rep.sites <- 3 #number of site visits
p.available <- NULL #availability probability needed for gdistsamp. Must be 1 for distsamp.
keyfun    <- NULL #key function needed for distance sampling

#time budget
t0 <- 0.1
th <- 0.001
tt <- 10

#detection function parameter
beta <- 0.01 #searcher efficiency
prob.detect <- seq(0.5, 0.99, length.out=20) #possible values for the probability of detection
ts.vec <- beta*prob.detect/(1 - prob.detect) #corresponding search times for the above detections

##Density specification
dens <- NULL #not needed for occupancy
alpha <- NULL #not needed for occupancy
prob.occ <- 0.5 #true probability of occupancy for occ or occRN

#Transect specification
#transect info
length <- 10 #length of transect
trans.hwidth <- 0.5 #half-width of transect
A <- length*2*trans.hwidth #area of a transect

B <- 1e3 #replicates to estimate standard error

#now run the simulation. Outputs a dataframe with columns ts (search time),
#se (standard error in probability of occupancy), cv (coefficient of variation
#in estimated probability of occupancy).
occ.out <- unmarked.sim(B=B, ts.vec=ts.vec, t0=t0, th=th, tt=tt, alpha=alpha, dens=dens,
                        A=A, trans.width=trans.width, beta=beta, prob.occ=prob.occ,
                        method=method, rep.sites=rep.sites, keyfun=keyfun,
                        p.available=p.available)

```

Below we see the output graphically, corresponding to an optimal search time of $\tau_S^* = 0.019$.

N-mixture model with unmarked

We can also look at the optimal search strategy in an N-mixture model. The N-mixture model code in `UnmarkedSims_pcount_example.R` is similar to the occupancy model, though we must define a few additional parameters to define the density and overdispersion.

```

library(unmarked)
source("Sim_funcs.R")

B <- 1e3 #replicates to estimate standard error

#method specific variables
method    <- "pcount"
keyfun    <- NULL #key function needed for distance sampling
rep.sites <- 3

```


Figure 2: Relative uncertainty in occupancy survey for different search times in an occupancy survey. Minimum of the curve corresponds to the optimal search time.

```
p.available <- NULL #availability probability needed for gdistsamp. Must be 1 for distsamp.
prob.occ <- NULL #probability of occupancy for occ or occRN

#time budget
t0 <- 0.1
th <- 0.001
tt <- 10

#detection function parameter
beta <- 0.01 #searcher efficiency
prob.detect <- seq(0.5, .99, length.out=10) #possible values for the probability of detection
ts.vec <- beta*prob.detect/(1 - prob.detect) #corresponding search times for the above detections

##Density specification
dens <- 1 #true density of targets
alpha <- 1/0.01 #overdispersion

#Transect specification
trans.length <- 10
trans.hwidth <- 1
Area <- trans.length*2*trans.hwidth

pcount.out <- unmarked.sim(B=B, ts.vec=ts.vec, t0=t0, th=th, tt=tt, alpha=alpha, dens=dens,
                           A=A, trans.width=trans.hwidth, beta=beta, prob.occ=prob.occ,
                           method=method, rep.sites=rep.sites, keyfun=keyfun,
                           p.available=p.available)
```

Here we simulated across three different values of overdispersion, with density = 1. We see that the optimal search time does decline with increases in overdispersion, consistent with our theoretical predictions.

Figure 3: Relative uncertainty in N-mixture model for three different levels of overdispersion. Minimum of the curve corresponds to the optimal search time.